

Integration Of Local History Of Batangas City: Basis For The Preparation Of Contextualized Module In Araling Panlipunan

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Publication Date: May 29, 2026

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20440189](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20440189)

Abstract

This study assessed the teachers' knowledge and integration of Batangas City's local history in teaching Araling Panlipunan among public junior high school teachers in the Division of Batangas City. Specifically, it aimed to determine the extent of manifestation of teachers' knowledge of local history in promoting cultural understanding among students, the degree of integration in terms of pedagogy, content, and evaluation tools, the relationship between teachers' knowledge and integration, the challenges encountered in teaching local history, and the development of a proposed contextualized module.

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design using a researcher-made questionnaire and interview as instruments. Respondents were 99 out of 132 public junior high school Araling Panlipunan teachers in the Division of Batangas City. Data were analyzed using ranking, percentage, weighted mean, and Pearson's r coefficient. Findings revealed that teachers highly manifested their knowledge of Batangas' local history, particularly in developing students' sense of belongingness, understanding of cultural roots, critical thinking, and awareness of contemporary issues. Teachers moderately integrated local history in their lessons, especially by including the economic history of Batangas and incorporating cultural artifacts into classroom activities. The grand mean indicated moderate integration across pedagogy, content, and evaluation tools. A strong and significant positive relationship ($r = .619-.813, p < .001$) was found between teachers' knowledge and the extent of integration, showing that deeper knowledge fosters stronger contextualization. Challenges included limited localized resources, lack of time, and inadequate training. The study concluded that integrating Batangas' local history enhances students' cultural identity and appreciation. It recommends curriculum localization, teacher capacity-building, and partnerships with local historians and institutions. A contextualized module highlighting Batangas' economic, political, and cultural heritage was proposed to make Araling Panlipunan teaching more relevant and meaningful.

Keywords: *Local History, Araling Panlipunan, Cultural Understanding, Contextualization, Batangas City.*

INTRODUCTION

Araling Panlipunan is an essential component of the basic education curriculum, as it helps instill values related to national pride, civic responsibility, and cultural awareness among students. This subject promotes awareness and engages students in real-world issues where they can critically analyze and understand various societal problems. This process strengthens values such as respect, responsibility, and accountability, which, in turn, help learners become responsible members of society.

However, existing literature shows that students often perceive history as a subject centered on rote memorization, resulting in negative attitudes, low engagement, and limited appreciation of the discipline (Ongsotto, 2013, as cited in Adanza et al., 2023; Eleazar, 2020; Potts, 2019). This gap between the intended goals of history education and actual classroom experiences highlights the need for more relevant and meaningful instructional approaches. One approach emphasized in several studies is the integration of local history in teaching.

Local history, defined as the study of the past within a specific locality such as Batangas City, provides a direct connection between historical content and students' lived experiences (Aiséirithe, 2019). Studies have shown that incorporating local history enhances students' interest, cultural awareness, and engagement by making learning more contextualized and relatable (Agon, 2021; Hritcu, 2024). Moreover, it fosters a sense of identity, belongingness, and civic responsibility, as students gain a deeper understanding of their community and their role within broader historical narratives (Dillard, 2019; Yefterson, 2020). Research further suggests that exposure to local history strengthens students' pride in their community and encourages active participation in social development (Pearson & Plevyak, 2020; Sariyatun & Marpelina, 2024).

In the Philippines, local history education is supported by several legal frameworks. The 1987 Constitution, particularly Article II, Section 13, and Article XIV, Section 3(2), emphasizes the importance of teaching history as a foundation for responsible citizenship. Furthermore, Republic Act No. 10086 emphasizes the conduct of research and the development of educational materials related to national and local history. Similarly, Republic Act No. 10533, or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, underscores the need for contextualization and localization in the curriculum, including the development of locally produced teaching materials that reflect the cultural and historical landscapes of different regions, including Batangas. This directive is further reinforced by Department of Education Memorandum Order No. 581, Series of 2023, which calls for the creation of localized and contextualized learning materials in Araling Panlipunan.

Despite these legal frameworks and recognized benefits, the integration of local history into Araling Panlipunan remains limited and inconsistent. Several studies identify key challenges, including the lack of instructional materials, limited teacher training, insufficient resources, and the absence of standardized content (Awa-ao & Roperez, 2024; De Claro, 2020; Colminar & Padullo, 2023). In addition, some teachers tend to focus on lower-order cognitive tasks, which hinder the development of students' critical thinking and historical skills (Mbatha & Moreeng,

2024). Curriculum constraints, time limitations, and varying levels of teacher preparedness further complicate the effective implementation of local history integration (Goksu & Somen, 2019; Kumar et al., 2023).

In response to these challenges, studies highlight the importance of integrating local history into the curriculum through localization and contextualization. The use of localized instructional materials, community-based resources, and innovative teaching strategies has been found to enhance the relevance and effectiveness of history instruction (Antezana, 2018; Cejas, 2023). Furthermore, the integration of technology, field-based learning, and collaboration with local communities contributes to a more engaging and meaningful learning experience (Morais, 2018; Santos, 2021).

However, there remains a noticeable gap in research focusing on the systematic and localized integration of history, particularly in specific areas such as Batangas City. While earlier studies have addressed general trends, benefits, and challenges, there is limited empirical evidence on how local history can be effectively integrated into Araling Panlipunan through structured and measurable approaches.

Furthermore, there is a scarcity of research on the integration of local history into education within Batangas City. While teachers may intend to include local history in their lessons, they are often constrained by a lack of accessible resources. For instance, the Batangas City library houses only a limited number of publications and journals about the city's history, underscoring the urgent need to document, preserve, and make accessible the province's rich cultural heritage. The researcher also observed that no prior research on local history has been conducted at Golden Gate Colleges.

This study sought to address these gaps by promoting the integration of Batangas' local history into Araling Panlipunan. By doing so, it aims to enrich educational materials, deepen students' cultural appreciation, and strengthen civic values, ultimately shaping learners who are more engaged, responsible, and connected to their community.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to enhance the teachers' knowledge of local history of Batangas City in teaching Araling Panlipunan subjects in the junior high schools of Batangas City Division. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of manifestation of teachers' knowledge of local history in promoting cultural understanding among students in terms of:
 - 1.1 sense of belongingness;
 - 1.2 understanding of cultural roots;
 - 1.3 Critical thinking; and
 - 1.4 Contemporary issues?

2. To what degree do teachers integrate the local history of Batangas City in teaching Araling Panlipunan in relation to:
 - 2.1 pedagogy;
 - 2.2 content; and
 - 2.3 evaluation tools?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of manifestation of teachers' knowledge and on the degree of integration of Batangas City local history?
4. What challenges do teachers encounter in integrating local history in teaching Araling Panlipunan?
5. Based on the results of the study, what contextualized module may be proposed?

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the assessment on the extent of manifestation of teachers' knowledge and on the degree of integration of local history of Batangas city.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the extent of teachers' knowledge regarding the value of local history and its integration in promoting cultural understanding among junior high school students in Batangas City. A validated, researcher-made Likert-type questionnaire was used as the primary instrument for data collection, supported by interviews to verify information related to local history. The qualitative data gathered provided deeper insights into teachers' perspectives and practices in integrating local history into classroom instruction. Based on the findings, the researcher developed a contextualized module aimed at enhancing the cultural understanding of junior high school teachers through the integration of local history in the Araling Panlipunan curriculum.

Participants

The teacher-respondents were ninety-nine (99) out of one hundred thirty-two (132) AP teachers in the junior high school from the 24 public high school in the Division of Batangas City. To determine the appropriate sample size, the **Raosoft sampling calculator** was utilized with a 5% margin of error. The researcher applied stratified proportionate sampling to ensure fair representation across the various strata of the population.

Data Gathering Instruments

A research-made questionnaire was used to gather the data about the extent of manifestation of teacher's integration of local history in teaching Araling Panlipunan. Interviews were also conducted to support and validate the quantitative findings.

Procedures

The researcher secured official permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Batangas City and the school principals. Before collecting any information, the researcher explained the study's purpose, risks, and benefits to the teacher-participants to ensure they understood their rights, including the freedom to withdraw at any time. The researcher strictly adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to keep all personal information private and secure. Data collection, including the distribution, retrieval, and scoring of questionnaires, was personally managed by the researcher to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Data Analysis

To analyze the data gathered from the respondents, this study employs a variety of statistical methods to ensure accurate interpretation. A structured questionnaire was used as the primary instrument to collect reliable information, which was then processed using the weighted mean to determine the average response for each item and provide a basis for verbal interpretation. Additionally, ranking was utilized to assess the relative importance or frequency of the participants' responses. Finally, *Pearson's r correlation* coefficient was applied to determine if a significant relationship exists between the teachers' knowledge of local history and their level of integration of these topics to promote cultural understanding.

Results and Discussion

Extent of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge of Local History in Promoting Cultural Understanding Among Students in Terms of Sense of Belongingness

As shown in Table 1, the data reveal that teachers highly manifested their knowledge of local history in promoting students' sense of belongingness, with a composite mean of 3.62. The highest mean score (3.74) indicates that teachers recognize that understanding family and community stories deepens students' connection and sense of belonging. This suggests that teachers strongly believe that learning about one's roots strengthens identity and cultural attachment.

Local history serves as a bridge connecting individuals to their heritage, enabling them to appreciate their origins and cultural identity. This finding supports Anderson's idea (as cited in Jati, 2023) that local narratives foster emotional connections and promote shared identity within communities.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score (3.32), interpreted as moderately manifested, refers to participation in community festivals and commemorations. This indicates that while teachers acknowledge the importance of such activities, their actual participation may be limited due to time constraints, accessibility, or other responsibilities.

Table 2. Extent of Manifestation of Teachers’ Knowledge of Local History in Promoting Cultural Understanding Among Students in Terms of Sense of Belongingness

<i>As an Araling Panlipunan teacher, I...</i>	WM	VI	RANK
1. feel connected to the community through historical knowledge	3.57	HM	8
2. appreciate local traditions, practices, and heritage	3.71	HM	3
3. participate in community or local festivals and commemorations	3.32	MM	10
4. value the role of community in shaping who I am today	3.70	HM	4.5
5. take pride in the shared struggles and achievements of Batangueños that foster unity and belongingness	3.73	HM	2
6. recognize that understanding family and community stories deepens my connection and sense of belonging	3.74	HM	1
7. see myself as part of the continuity of Batangas’ heritage	3.62	HM	7
8. acknowledge that preserving local traditions nurtures both my cultural pride and my sense of belonging	3.70	HM	4.5
9. manifest a deeper sense of belonging when I witness the unity of Batangueños during historical commemorations and community events	3.64	HM	6
10. consider myself an active member of the Batangas community, with my sense of belonging rooted in its local history	3.49	MM	9
COMPOSITE	3.62	HM	

Legend: *HM* (Highly Manifested) *MM* (Moderately Manifested) *SM* (Slightly Manifested) *LM* (Least Manifested)

Overall, the findings suggest that teachers possess strong knowledge of local history as a means of fostering belongingness. This supports Sariyatun and Marpelina (2024), who emphasized that integrating local history strengthens identity, community connection, and cultural awareness among learners. They explained that such integration not only fosters a sense of belongingness but also builds a deeper connection with the community. Moreover, it enhances students’ understanding of their cultural roots while developing essential skills such as critical thinking and problem-solving. These findings affirm that teaching local history plays a vital role in cultivating both cultural awareness and intellectual growth among learners.

Extent of Manifestation of Teachers’ Knowledge of Local History in Promoting Cultural Understanding Among Students in Terms of Understanding of Cultural Roots

As presented in Table 3, teachers demonstrated a high level of manifestation in promoting cultural understanding in terms of cultural roots, with a composite mean of 3.56. The highest mean (3.75) shows that teachers emphasize the importance of local heroes, historical sites, and landmarks in shaping Batangas’ heritage.

Table 3. Extent of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge of Local History in Promoting Cultural Understanding Among Students in Terms of Understanding of Cultural Roots

<i>As an Araling Panlipunan teacher, I...</i>	WM	VI	RANK
1. identify the importance of local heroes, historical sites and landmarks in shaping Batangas' heritage	3.75	HM	1
2. trace and highlight the contributions of families and communities to the historical development of Batangas	3.45	MM	8.5
3. recognize and explain how the past influences present-day practices, values, and traditions	3.64	HM	3
4. guide students to narrate and discuss meaningful stories about their community's history and culture	3.55	HM	5.5
5. explore the evolution of Batangueño language and expressions as reflections of cultural identity	3.44	MM	10
6. discuss the historical significance of local crafts and industries in the economic and cultural life of Batangas	3.59	HM	4
7. encourage students to conduct interviews with elders to learn more about Batangas' past	3.45	MM	8.5
8. compare Batangas' cultural practices with those of other provinces to deepen understanding and appreciation	3.55	HM	5.5
9. demonstrate respect for cultural artifacts, language, and traditions handed down from our ancestors	3.54	HM	7
10. help students understand how historical challenges shaped Batangueños' resilience and local identity	3.66	HM	2
	COMPOSITE	3.56	HM

Legend: *HM* (Highly Manifested) *MM* (Moderately Manifested) *SM* (Slightly Manifested) *LM* (Least Manifested)

This indicates that teachers recognize these elements as essential tools in helping students appreciate their cultural identity. By integrating these components into instruction, students gain a deeper understanding of their historical background and cultural heritage.

However, some indicators, such as tracing community contributions and encouraging interviews with elders (mean = 3.45), were only moderately manifested. This suggests that although teachers value community-based learning, such practices are not consistently implemented, possibly due to limited time and resources.

These findings align with Laeen et al. (2019), who noted that community-based activities are often constrained by logistical and institutional limitations. Nevertheless, such approaches remain essential in promoting authentic and meaningful learning experiences.

Overall, the results affirm that teachers play a significant role in strengthening students' cultural roots, consistent with DepEd policies and Republic Act No. 10086, which emphasize the importance of integrating local history into education. By integrating lessons related to Batangas' local heritage, teachers not only enhance students' historical understanding but also cultivate pride, identity, and respect for their roots, fundamental elements in fostering cultural understanding and national consciousness.

Extent of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge of Local History in Promoting Cultural Understanding Among Students in Terms of Understanding of Cultural Roots

Table 4 shows that teachers highly manifested their knowledge of local history in promoting students' critical thinking skills, with a composite mean of 3.55. The highest mean scores (3.62) indicate that teachers effectively guide students in evaluating the credibility of sources and questioning unverified historical narratives.

Table 4. Extent of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge of Local History in Promoting Cultural Understanding Among Students in Terms of Critical Thinking

<i>As an Araling Panlipunan teacher, I...</i>	WM	VI	RANK
1. analyze historical events from multiple perspectives to provide students with a broader understanding of the past	3.52	H M	8
2. identify biases and gaps in historical narratives to model critical thinking for my students	3.53	H M	6.5
3. draw meaningful connections between past events and present societal issues to make history relevant to learners	3.57	H M	4
4. promote the comparison of Batangas' history with that of other places to highlight similarities and differences in cultural experiences	3.51	H M	9
5. evaluate the accuracy and reliability of historical accounts before presenting them to students	3.53	H M	6.5
6. promote reasoned arguments and discussions about cultural and historical topics to foster critical thinking	3.54	H M	5
7. help students evaluate the credibility of local history sources to strengthen their analytical skills	3.62	H M	1.5
8. encourage students to question myths or unverified stories by guiding them toward evidence-based perspectives	3.62	H M	1.5
9. integrate problem-solving activities using historical scenarios to develop students' decision-making skills	3.49	M M	10
10. relate local historical events to present-day decision-making processes to emphasize the relevance of history in daily life	3.58	H M	3
COMPOSITE	3.55	H M	

Legend: *HM* (Highly Manifested) *MM* (Moderately Manifested) *SM* (Slightly Manifested) *LM* (Least Manifested)

This suggests that teachers are actively promoting analytical thinking and evidence-based learning. Students are encouraged to critically examine historical information rather than passively accept it.

Moreover, teachers demonstrated strong practices in analyzing events from multiple perspectives and comparing local and global histories. These approaches help students understand that historical narratives are shaped by diverse contexts.

The findings support Mbatha and Moreeng (2024), who emphasized the importance of using history to develop higher-order thinking skills. Similarly, Gunawan and Rachmah (2021) highlighted that understanding historical context enhances critical analysis.

In general, the grand mean of 3.55, verbally interpreted as highly manifested, indicates that teachers consistently demonstrate knowledge and practices that use local history as a means to enhance students' critical thinking. These results shows that teachers recognize local history not just a record of the past but as a powerful medium for inquiry and reflection. Through the integration of localized content, teachers help students connect historical experiences with contemporary issues, develop analytical reasoning, and cultivate respect for cultural heritage. These findings affirm the statements of Sariyatun and Marpelina (2024), who both asserted that teaching local history deepens understanding, strengthens identity, and develops critical and problem-solving skills essential for responsible citizenship and cultural appreciation.

Extent of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge of Local History in Promoting Cultural Understanding Among Students in Terms of Contemporary Issues

As shown in Table 5, teachers highly manifested their knowledge of local history in connecting it to contemporary issues, with a composite mean of 3.58. The highest mean (3.74) indicates that teachers help students understand the role of culture and tradition in shaping identity in a globalized world.

This finding suggests that teachers successfully relate historical knowledge to present-day realities, making learning more relevant and meaningful. It was supported by the study of Yefterson (2020), who emphasized that local history fosters a sense of belonging and national identity, as it allows learners to see how their cultural heritage connects to broader social contexts.

Additionally, teachers emphasized resilience and community strength, as reflected in historical experiences. This approach helps students draw lessons from the past and apply them to current societal challenges.

These findings are consistent with Yefterson (2020) and Barbour (2023), who highlighted that local history strengthens identity and helps learners understand contemporary social issues.

Overall, the results show that teachers highly manifested the effective integration of local history in addressing contemporary issues, as revealed by the findings with a composite mean of 3.58. This indicates that teachers in Batangas are not only imparting historical knowledge but are also guiding students to apply historical understanding to modern social, cultural, and political contexts. This finding supported by Sariyatun and Marpelina (2024), who emphasized that integrating local history enhances students' sense of identity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills relevant to present day challenges.

Table 5. Extent of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge of Local History in Promoting Cultural Understanding Among Students in Terms of Contemporary Issues

<i>As an Araling Panlipunan teacher, I...</i>	WM	VI	RANK
1. link lessons on local historical events to current social, political, and cultural issues	3.72	HM	2
2. propose possible solutions to present-day challenges inspired by historical insights	3.61	HM	3.5
3. recognize recurring themes of struggle and reasoning in history and emphasize their relevance today	3.59	HM	5
4. understand the role of culture and tradition in shaping identity amid globalization	3.74	HM	1
5. actively participate in discussions that promote the preservation of culture in modern times	3.49	MM	9
6. explore changes in community roles over time to help students appreciate social development	3.56	HM	6
7. connect past health crises to modern-day public health issues to draw meaningful lessons	3.48	MM	10
8. highlight historical resilience in times of disaster to inspire present-day strength and unity	3.51	HM	8
9. encourage community-based solutions that are informed and inspired by local history	3.53	HM	7
10. help students identify lessons from history that can be applied in solving current problems	3.61	HM	3.5
COMPOSITE	3.58	HM	

Legend: *HM* (Highly Manifested) *MM* (Moderately Manifested) *SM* (Slightly Manifested) *LM* (Least Manifested)

Teachers' Degree of Integration of the Local History of Batangas City in Teaching Araling Panlipunan in terms of Pedagogy

As shown in Table 6, the data revealed that teachers moderately integrated local history through the use of role-play activities to depict significant historical moments in Batangas, with a mean value of 3.33. This means that teachers occasionally use role-play to help students relive important events and understand the experiences of historical figures. Such activities make learning more interactive and engaging for students. In line with this, Santos (2021) supported the idea that innovative teaching strategies, such as role-playing and creative simulations to make learning history more meaningful and relevant to students by connecting them with local contexts.

Table 6. Teachers Degree of Integration of the Local History of Batangas City in Teaching Araling Panlipunan in terms of Pedagogy

<i>As an Araling Panlipunan teacher, I...</i>	WM	VI	RANK
1. prepare lesson plans that integrate Batangas local history content	3.08	MI	9
2. adapt participatory activities such as group discussions and field trips to heritage sites to strengthen students' attachment to the community	3.09	MI	8
3. use role-play activities to depict significant historical moments in Batangas	3.33	MI	1
4. adopt project-based learning approaches centered on Batangas local history	3.19	MI	3.5
5. facilitate collaborative group work that highlights Batangas' heritage	3.21	MI	2
6. utilize digital tools to creatively present Batangas' historical events	3.19	MI	3.5
7. design interactive games that reinforce knowledge of Batangas' history	3.15	MI	7
8. incorporate educational trips to historical sites in Batangas to deepen students' cultural appreciation	3.17	MI	6
9. invite guest speakers who are knowledgeable about Batangas' history to enrich classroom learning	3.01	MI	10
10. integrate Batangas local history into other subject areas to provide interdisciplinary connections	3.18	MI	5
COMPOSITE	3.16	MI	

Legend: *HI* (Highly Integrated) *MI* (Moderately Integrated) *SI* (Slightly Integrated) *LI* (Least Integrated)

The lowest mean value of 3.09 indicates that teachers moderately integrated participatory activities such as group discussions and field trips to heritage sites to strengthen students' attachment to the community. This means that while teachers recognize the importance of such activities, they may face challenges in organizing them regularly due to time or resource limitations. This was supported by Barbour (2023), who emphasized that local field trips and community-based learning enhance students' understanding of their community's identity and heritage, making local history more meaningful.

In general, the composite mean of 3.16, interpreted as moderately integrated, means that while teachers recognize the importance of integrating Batangas local history into their lessons, its consistent application remains limited. This also indicates a need for more training, resources, and support from educational institutions to promote deeper integration of local history in Araling Panlipunan classes. This finding was aligned with Goksu and Somen (2019) and Buenaflor (2024), who both emphasized that proper integration of local history enhances students' understanding of their identity and community but requires structured support, localized materials, and teacher preparation.

Teachers' Degree of Integration of the Local History of Batangas City in Teaching Araling Panlipunan in terms of Content

As reflected in Table 7, the data show that teachers moderately integrated their knowledge of local history in Include economic history of Batangas in their lessons which got a

mean value of 3.37. This indicates that teachers recognize the importance of connecting the province's economic development to its historical growth, helping students understand how trade, industry, and livelihood shaped Batangas' progress. Including economic history in lessons allows learners to relate past economic activities to present realities, strengthening appreciation for local contributions to the Philippine economy. According to Maghirang (2025), local economies like that of Batangas played a vital role in shaping regional and national identities.

Table 7. Teachers Degree of Integration of The Local History of Batangas City in Teaching Araling Panlipunan in terms of Content

<i>As an Araling Panlipunan teacher, I...</i>	WM	VI	RANK
1. feature significant historical events of Batangas in my teaching topics	3.32	MI	2
2. present notable Batangueños in historical discussions	3.17	MI	8
3. discuss Batangas' role in national historical events	3.18	MI	7
4. relate Batangas' history to the Philippine independence movements	3.31	MI	3
5. highlight the use of local primary sources in my lessons	3.19	MI	6
6. integrate Batangas' cultural artifacts into classroom activities	3.09	MI	10
7. incorporate Batangas' folk tales into relevant topics	3.20	MI	5
8. connect how Batangas historical places affects the economy	3.27	MI	4
9. include the economic history of Batangas in my lessons	3.37	MI	1
10. use maps and visuals to show Batangas' historical geography	3.12	MI	9
COMPOSITE			3.22 MI

Legend: *HI* (Highly Integrated) *MI* (Moderately Integrated) *SI* (Slightly Integrated) *LI* (Least Integrated)

On the other hand, teachers moderately integrated their knowledge of local history in discussing Batangas' role in national historical events, which obtained a mean value of 3.18. This suggests that teachers placed less emphasis on highlighting Batangas' contributions to broader national narratives. Strengthening this aspect could further deepen students' understanding of how local events play a vital role in shaping national history. This is supported by Barbour (2023), who emphasized the importance of connecting local histories to the national context to help learners appreciate the interconnectedness of historical developments.

Teachers Degree of Integration of the Local History of Batangas City in Teaching Araling Panlipunan in terms of Evaluation Tools

Table 8 showed that teachers highly integrated the economic history of Batangas into their lessons, with a weighted mean of 3.21. This means that by connecting Batangas' local history with broader national contexts, teachers encourage students to think critically about how events in their own communities influenced or were influenced by nationwide issues. This was supported by Dillard (2019), who highlighted that local history acts as a bridge between students' immediate experiences and larger historical narratives, enhancing understanding and engagement.

Table 8. Teachers Degree of Integration of the Local History of Batangas City in Teaching Araling Panlipunan in terms of Evaluation Tools

<i>As an Araling Panlipunan teacher, I...</i>	WM	VI	RANK
1. prepare tests with questions on Batangas' local history	3.04	MI	7.5
2. provide students opportunity to write research papers that connect historical roots to contemporary issues	3.04	MI	7.5
3. require reflection papers based on visits to Batangas' historical sites	2.98	MI	10
4. create performance tasks that focus on Batangas' culture	3.09	MI	3
5. evaluate students through oral presentations on Batangas' local history	3.02	MI	9
6. assess students through creative outputs that showcase Batangas' history	3.06	MI	5.5
7. develop rubrics that assess students' appreciation of local heritage	3.06	MI	5.5
8. include the analysis of primary sources from Batangas in student assessments	3.07	MI	4
9. integrate local history themes into Araling Panlipunan quarterly examinations	3.15	MI	2
10. assess students' ability to connect Batangas' local history to national issues	3.21	MI	1
COMPOSITE 3.07 MI			

Legend: *HI* (Highly Integrated) *MI* (Moderately Integrated) *SI* (Slightly Integrated) *LI* (Least Integrated)

In contrast, teachers have moderately integrated the connection of Batangas historical places to the local economy in their lessons, with a mean of 3.09. This indicates that while teachers occasionally link historical landmarks to economic developments, this practice is moderately applied and not fully consistent. Connecting local sites to economic contexts helps students understand how Batangas' historical experiences shaped its contemporary economic transformation, including its shift from agriculture to industrial and tourism activities (Maghirang, 2025). By highlighting the historical roots of economic growth, teachers encourage students to see the relevance of local history in understanding present-day community development. Strengthening this approach can foster greater historical awareness and civic appreciation among students.

The results of the study also revealed that teachers moderately integrated Batangas' local history in their Araling Panlipunan classes, with a composite mean of 3.07, interpreted as moderately integrated. This suggests that while efforts are being made to incorporate local history, its implementation is not yet consistent or fully maximized.

Relationship between the Extent of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge and on the Degree of Integration of Batangas City Local History

The table 9 presented the relationship between the teachers' knowledge of local history and the extent of its integration in teaching, particularly in promoting a sense of belongingness among students. The results revealed strong positive correlations across all areas, in pedagogy with r-value of .577, content with r-value of .619, and evaluation tools with r-value of .568 indicating that all relationships are statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the assessment of the manifestation of teachers' knowledge and the extent of integration of Batangas City local history is rejected. This means that as teachers demonstrate higher knowledge of local history, the degree to which they effectively integrate local history into their teaching also increases, especially in fostering students' connection and sense of identity with their community.

Among the three variables, the content showed the strongest correlation, suggesting that when teachers possess a deeper understanding of Batangas City's local history and cultural heritage, they are more capable of designing meaningful lessons that strengthen students' pride and sense of belonging. Meanwhile, pedagogy and evaluation tools, though slightly lower, also play vital roles, implying that teaching methods and assessment practices grounded in local history significantly contribute to nurturing students' appreciation of their roots.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers' knowledge of local history is a key factor in promoting students' sense of belongingness, and that integrating local heritage meaningfully in lessons leads to a more culturally rooted and community-oriented learning experience.

Table 9. Relationship between the Assessment of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge and on the Extent of Integration of Batangas City Local History in Terms of Sense of Belongingness

	<i>r-value</i>	<i>Degree</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision on H0</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
<i>Sense of Belongingness</i>					
1. Pedagogy	.577	Strong	<.001	Reject	Significant
2. Content	.619	Strong	<.001	Reject	Significant
3. Evaluation Tools	.568	Strong	<.001	Reject	Significant

Relationship between the Assessment of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge and on the Extent of Integration of Batangas City Local History in terms of Understanding Cultural Roots

Table 10 showed the relationship between the teachers' knowledge of local history and the extent of its integration in teaching, particularly in promoting students' understanding of their cultural roots. The results revealed strong positive correlations across all areas, with pedagogy showing an r-value of .701, content with an r-value of .794, and evaluation tools with an r-value of .606, all statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the assessment of the manifestation of teachers' knowledge and the extent

of integration of Batangas City local history is rejected. This indicates that as teachers demonstrate higher knowledge of local history, the degree to which they effectively integrate local heritage into their teaching also increases, particularly in helping students understand and appreciate their cultural roots.

Among the three variables, content showed the strongest correlation, suggesting that when teachers have a deeper understanding of Batangas City's history, traditions, and cultural heritage, they are better equipped to design lessons that effectively communicate the significance of local culture and foster students' cultural awareness. Pedagogy and evaluation tools, while slightly lower, also play crucial roles, indicating that teaching strategies and assessment practices grounded in local history significantly contribute to students' comprehension of their cultural identity.

Overall, the findings highlight that teachers' knowledge of local history is a critical factor in enhancing students' understanding of cultural roots. Effective integration of local heritage through meaningful lesson content, appropriate teaching methods, and well-structured evaluation tools provides students with opportunities to connect their personal experiences to the broader cultural and historical context of Batangas, fostering a deeper appreciation of their community's identity and heritage

Table 10
Relationship between the Assessment of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge and on the Extent of Integration of Batangas City Local History in terms of Understanding Cultural Roots

	<i>r-value</i>	<i>Degree</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision on H0</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
<i>Understanding Cultural Roots</i>					
1. Pedagogy	.701	Strong	<.001	Reject	Reject
2. Content	.794	Strong	<.001	Reject	Reject
3. Evaluation Tools	.606	Strong	<.001	Reject	Reject

Relationship between the Assessment of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge and on the Extent of Integration of Batangas City Local History in terms of Critical Thinking

The presentation of data in Table 11 is about the correlation between the teachers' knowledge of local history and the extent of its integration in teaching, particularly in enhancing students' critical thinking skills. The results revealed strong positive correlations across all areas, with pedagogy showing an r-value of .702, content with an r-value of .813, and evaluation tools with an r-value of .655, all statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between the assessment of the manifestation of teachers' knowledge and the extent of integration of Batangas City local history, is rejected. This indicates that as teachers demonstrate higher knowledge of local history, the degree to which they effectively integrate local history into their teaching also increases, especially in promoting students' ability to think critically about historical events, cultural practices, and their community.

In the three variables, content exhibited the strongest correlation, suggesting that teachers' mastery of Batangas City's local history and cultural heritage is crucial in designing lesson materials and activities that challenge students to analyze, evaluate, and draw connections between past and present events. Pedagogy and evaluation tools, although slightly lower, also play essential roles, emphasizing that the methods teachers use to deliver lessons and assess learning outcomes significantly influence the development of students' critical thinking.

The findings highlight that teachers' knowledge of local history is a key factor in cultivating students' critical thinking skills. By integrating local historical content through well-planned lessons, innovative teaching strategies, and carefully designed assessments, students are encouraged to engage deeply with historical narratives, reflect on their implications, and make informed judgments. This approach not only strengthens students' analytical abilities but also helps them understand the relevance of local history in shaping contemporary society and community life.

Table 11
Relationship between the Assessment of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge and on the Extent of Integration of Batangas City Local History in terms of Critical Thinking

	r-value	Degree	p-value	Decision on H0	Interpretation
<i>Critical Thinking</i>					
1. Pedagogy	.702	Strong	<.001	Reject	Significant
2. Content	.813	Strong	<.001	Reject	Significant
3. Evaluation Tools	.655	Strong	<.001	Reject	Significant

Relationship between the Assessment of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge and on the Extent of Integration of Batangas City Local History in terms of Contemporary Issues

Shown in the Table 12 is the correlation between the teachers' knowledge of local history and the extent of its integration in teaching, particularly in addressing contemporary issues. The results revealed strong positive correlations across all areas, with pedagogy showing an r-value of .623, content with an r-value of .717, and evaluation tools with an r-value of .540, all statistically significant at $p < .001$. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between the assessment of the manifestation of teachers' knowledge and the extent of integration of Batangas City local history, is rejected. This indicates that as teachers demonstrate higher knowledge of local history, the degree to which they integrate it into their teaching also increases, particularly in enabling students to connect historical events to contemporary societal issues.

With all the data presented, the strongest correlation is about the content, suggesting that teachers' mastery of Batangas' historical and cultural heritage is critical for developing lessons that allow students to analyze current social, political, and economic issues in light of their

historical roots. Pedagogy and evaluation tools, while slightly lower, remain essential, highlighting that the teaching methods and assessment practices employed by knowledgeable teachers play a significant role in helping students apply historical understanding to contemporary challenges.

General findings underscore that teachers' knowledge of local history is a key factor in linking past experiences to present-day issues. Effective integration of local history through meaningful lesson content, engaging teaching strategies, and well-designed evaluation tools empowers students to critically assess modern societal concerns, understand their community's historical contributions, and become more informed and responsible citizens.

Table 12

Relationship between the Assessment of Manifestation of Teachers' Knowledge and on the Extent of Integration of Batangas City Local History in terms of Contemporary Issues

	r-value	Degree	p-value	Decision on H0	Interpretation
<i>Contemporary Issues</i>					
1. Pedagogy	.623	Strong	<.001	Reject	Significant
2. Content	.717	Strong	<.001	Reject	Significant
3. Evaluation Tools	.540	Strong	<.001	Reject	Significant

Challenges Encountered in Integrating Local History in Teaching Araling Panlipunan

The study revealed that while teachers recognize the importance of integrating Batangas' local history into Araling Panlipunan, several challenges hinder the consistent and effective implementation of these practices. By identifying and understanding these obstacles, the study provides a foundation for recommending strategies to enhance the integration of local history into the teaching-learning process, thereby enriching students' learning experiences and cultural awareness.

It was highlighted in Table 13 that one of the challenges encountered by teachers in integrating Batangas' local history in teaching Araling Panlipunan pertains to the preparation of tests with questions on Batangas' local history, which had a mean of 3.12. This indicates that designing assessments aligned with local content is difficult, requiring considerable time and careful curriculum alignment. Teachers also often lack locally developed test items or sample questions, which limits their ability to effectively evaluate students' understanding of Batangas' history.

The study revealed that teachers moderately encountered challenges in evaluating students through oral presentations on local history, with a mean value of 2.94. This suggests that factors such as large class sizes, time constraints, and the lack of clear assessment frameworks limit the use of interactive evaluation methods. Despite these challenges, oral presentations are valuable for developing communication skills, critical thinking, and engagement with cultural content. As noted by Santos (2021), participatory approaches, such as student-led discussions and

experiential learning, enhance students' connection to local culture and history. Thus, addressing logistical barriers and integrating oral assessments more effectively can enrich students' learning experiences and deepen their appreciation of Batangas' cultural identity.

All of these challenge highlights the gap between the pedagogical value of experiential learning and practical constraints, pointing to the need for resources, planning, and creative solutions. The results revealed a composite mean of 3.02, which is verbally interpreted as moderately encountered. This means that teachers sometimes face difficulties in including local historical content in their lessons and assessments, though they still make consistent efforts to do so. These challenges are mainly due to limited resources, lack of localized assessment tools, and logistical constraints. Despite these, teachers continue to make efforts to promote local history awareness, showing their commitment to developing students' cultural understanding and appreciation of their heritage.

Table 13
Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Integrating Local History of Batangas in Teaching Araling Panlipunan

<i>As an Araling Panlipunan teacher, I...</i>	WM	VI	RANK
1. prepare tests with questions on Batangas' local history	3.12	ME	1
2. provide students opportunity to write research papers that connect historical roots to contemporary issues	2.99	ME	5.5
3. require reflection papers based on visits to Batangas' historical sites	3.09	ME	2
4. create performance tasks that focus on Batangas' culture	3.02	ME	3
5. evaluate students through oral presentations on Batangas' local history	2.94	ME	8
6. assess students through creative outputs that showcase Batangas' history	2.99	ME	5.5
7. develop rubrics that assess students' appreciation of local heritage	2.96	ME	7
8. include the analysis of primary sources from Batangas in student assessments	2.85	ME	10
9. integrate local history themes into Araling Panlipunan quarterly examinations	3.00	ME	4
10. assess students' ability to connect Batangas' local history to national issues	2.90	ME	9
COMPOSITE	3.02	ME	

Legend: *HE* (Highly Encountered) *ME* (Moderately Encountered) *SE* (Slightly Encountered) *LE* (Least Encountered)

Proposed Contextualized Module in Araling Panlipunan.

Based on the findings, a contextualized learning module on Batangas' local history is proposed to enhance teachers' integration of local content and ensure instructional consistency in teaching

Araling Panlipunan. The proposed module will focus on the economic, political, and cultural heritage of Batangas, aiming to develop students' critical thinking, cultural awareness, and sense of identity. It will provide structured and curriculum-aligned materials that guide teachers in designing interactive lessons and assessments connecting local and national historical contexts. This initiative seeks to strengthen the integration of local history in classroom instruction, making the teaching of Araling Panlipunan more relevant, meaningful, and contextually grounded in the learners' community experiences.

LINK to access the Contextualized Module: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Kc50iJewO-FkJmrVIod2_eiLK72KuSrW/view?usp=sharing

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Teacher's knowledge of local history was found highly manifested in promoting cultural understanding.
2. The integration of Batangas' local history in teaching Araling Panlipunan is moderately practiced.
3. There is a significant relationship between the assessment on the teachers' knowledge of local history and on its degree of integration in the lesson, indicating that teachers who demonstrate a higher level of knowledge about local history tend to integrate it more effectively in their Araling Panlipunan instruction.
4. Teachers face moderate challenges in integrating local history, including limited instructional materials, scarce local references, and logistical constraints for field-based learning. Despite this, they remain committed to promoting the province's heritage and identity through creative and innovative approaches.
5. The study confirms that integrating local history enhances students' sense of belongingness, critical thinking, and cultural appreciation, aligning with DepEd's goal of localizing and contextualizing instruction to make learning more meaningful and reflective of Filipino identity.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The authorities may review the prepared contextualized module before its possible utilization.
2. Teachers may enhance their teaching methods by using storytelling, project-based learning, digital tools, and interactive activities that connect students to local heritage.
3. For future researchers, it is recommended to explore students' perspectives on localized instruction, conduct comparative studies with other provinces, and develop validated contextualized modules on Batangas' local history for junior high schools.

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